

Impact of School Feeding Program and Teaching Methods on School Attendance among Junior Secondary School Students in Kebbi State

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Abstract

School attendance is a global phenomenon that merits consideration among various stakeholders owing to its importance in both human and economic development of any country. This study therefore, focused on the impact of School Feeding Program (SFP) and teaching method on school attendance among Junior Secondary school students in Kebbi state. Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant. Descriptive research design of expo facto type was used. Three hundred (300) students were randomly selected and formed the participants for the study, 30 each from the 10 randomly selected schools. Three research instruments were adapted and used in the study, they are, School feeding program (0.73), Teaching Method (0.87) and School Attendance scales (0.74). The result shows that the school feeding program, the teaching methods (visual, kinesthetic, and auditory elements), and student attendance are all combined ($R^2 = 30.18$, $F(4,295) = 0.69$, $p < .05$). The school feeding program and the visual, kinesthetic, and auditory components together accounted for 29% of the change in self-reported student attendance. This demonstrated that the school feeding program, together with the visual, kinesthetic, and auditory components, have a significant impact on student attendance. Additionally, only the school feeding program ($\beta = .54$, $t = 10.86$, $p < .05$) was found to be a significant independent predictor of school attendance, while the visual ($\beta = -.02$, $t = -0.31$, $p > .05$), kinesthetic ($\beta = -.01$, $t = -0.16$, $p > .05$), and audio ($\beta = -.07$, $t = -1.109$) methods of teaching were found to be significant independent predictors. $p > .05$. The findings of this study have established that school feeding programs has a significant positive impact on school attendance. Additionally, it has been observed that teaching method has a significant positive relationship on student attendance. It was recommended that, government should consider the sustainability of school feeding program particularly at the basic level. Teachers should use interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, problem-solving method, and hands-on activities to make learning more interesting and engaging.

Keywords: school feeding program, teaching method, school attendanc

Introduction

Student absenteeism is a global phenomenon that merits consideration among various educational stakeholders. According to Freire (2018), education and school attendance serve to promote cultural/political freedom and societal reform. The teaching of skills for students to develop and implement a particular societal norm, the promotion of ethical values, and the development of students' independence ought to be the primary focuses. This is very much represented by humanistic instructional methods of reasoning, for example, the secret educational program, which is fundamental the conventional educational program, considers moral way of behaving and creating qualities like legitimate group working abilities (Martimianakis & Hafferty, 2016).

The implementation of moral, cultural, and behavioral change is significantly influenced by these secondary school education concepts. The transition from the 6-5-4 system of education to the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1998 has a significant impact on a child's physical and mental development, demonstrating that secondary education is vital to Nigerian higher education. A child can attend primary school for six years, junior secondary school for three years, and senior secondary

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school for three years, and tertiary education for four years under the 6-3-3-4 system. Simply put, the National Policy on Education must be consulted whenever a discussion of the significance of secondary education in Nigeria is initiated. Section 5 of the national policy on education does, however, highlight a portion of the significance of secondary education in Nigeria. This goes a long way toward demonstrating the significance of secondary education in Nigeria from the stage of policy formulation. In addition, it is ideal to take into consideration the enduring significance of secondary education in Nigeria.

1. Give more junior secondary school students, regardless of social, religious, or ethnic background, the chance to pursue higher education.
2. A diversified curriculum to accommodate students' varying talents, opportunities, and roles after secondary school.
3. Provide students with the tools they need to thrive in today's technologically advanced society.
4. Promote Nigerian culture, language, and art, as well as the global cultural heritage.
5. Raise an age of individuals who can have an independent perspective, regard the sensations of others, regard the poise of work, and value those values determined under our expansive public points, and live as one resident.
6. Cultivate Nigerian solidarity with an accentuation on the normal lines that joins us.
7. Inspire students to strive for success and personal growth, both in school and later in life.

In particular, the educational statistics report that was published in 2018 by the National Bureau of Statistics revealed that 1,051,670 students attend private junior secondary schools while 4,787,317 students attend public junior secondary schools. In addition, the report revealed that 911,561 students attend private senior secondary schools and 4,475,309 students attend public senior secondary schools. These numbers were all higher than those recorded in 2015. This shows that auxiliary school training in Nigeria is setting aside more space for additional members. Notably is the fact that these schools are dispersed throughout various communities in Nigeria, providing everyone with equal opportunities. According to available evidence, junior secondary attendance rates in Nigeria are sluggish and somewhat inconsistent. The profile of junior optional school training in Nigeria uncovers that school participation has generally expanding over the course of the years with the most noteworthy development pace of 219.64 percent in 1997 and the least development rate Public Department of Measurements in 2004. However, Nigeria's secondary school attendance changed significantly between 1995 and 2004. This is primarily because of the political crisis, unrest, agricultural conflict, and industrial dispute that occurred during these times. Despite the government's commitment over time to encourage education at all levels through a variety of policy interventions and school feeding programs, school attendance rates for children of school age remain extremely low. Aside from this, documentary evidence of the impact of education on junior secondary school attendance is still very low, particularly in the northern region of Kebbi State. This is due to parents' low literacy levels and lack of awareness of the importance of school attendance; however, rather than encouraging their children to attend school regularly, they engage their children in activities such as farming, fishing, cattle rearing, trading, hawking, and apprenticeships when they are school-age. The majority of children drop out of school early, after primary education, according to other studies. The government has devised a strategy to halt this trend by implementing a school feeding program (SFP) to raise junior secondary school attendance indices. The School Feeding Program is a crucial initiative that has been implemented in a number of developed and developing nations to combat hunger, improve student performance, and increase attendance at school. Adelman, Gilligan, and Lehrer, (2008), concluded that 40% of hungry children in developing countries attend school each day. As a result, providing school meals is detrimental to children's nutrition. Instead of keeping their children at home to work or to care for siblings and engage them in other activities like agriculture, farming, hawking, and fishing, parents are encouraged to send them to school. Poverty and hunger have prevented many children from attending school. In addition, these kids are more likely to drop out of school for the reason that they have to take care of their direct needs for survival before they can prepare for school. As a result, stumpy school appearance, low lesson attendance, and high school dropouts are frequent issues in the education of children from poor homes, particularly in regions with high levels of food insecurity. Even though both private and social returns to education are acknowledged to be high, the level of education achievement has also been stumpy in many emergent nations (Gilligan, 2008). However, it is undisputed that in poor families, in addition to hunger, other forms of poverty also affect school attendance.

The essential goal of the SFP is to diminish hunger among younger students. According to the World Food Report, it is also predictable that school attendance, peer friendship, retention, and completion rates will rise, particularly among children living in poor rural and urban neighborhoods. It improves students' comprehension and learning abilities while also improving the nutritional status of schoolchildren. In order to ensure that every child in Nigeria has access to free, compulsory, and universal basic education, the FGN implemented the SFP. A total of 2.5 million children, or 10% of the population, are expected to participate in the program that aims to provide every child in Nigerian schools with one meal per day. In addition to encouraging local food production and increasing farmers' incomes, the program increased school attendance, particularly

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among rural and poor urban children. The School Feeding Program was established in the 1930s in the United Kingdom and the United States with the clear intention of enhancing children's development (Richter, Griesel, & Rose, 2000). Baker, Elwood, Jones, Hughes, and Sweetnam (1997), emphasized that it was a program in the UK that provided free milk to schoolchildren began in 1934.

World Food Report describes the organized School Feeding Programme as a program that aids in community development, education, and health while also reducing hunger. If students regularly attended school, school feeding can be provided in the form of meals or snacks to be consumed during school hours or distributed as dry take-home food rations at the end of each day, month, or school term (Uwameiye & Salami, 2013). According to Uwameiye & Salami (2013), it serves as a platform for supporting children and their families in a variety of contexts. The provision of high-quality and sufficient educational facilities for adolescents is one of the pillars upon which a nation is constructed. People's lives are shaped into political leaders, scientists, economists, artists, and free thinkers through education (Food and Agriculture Organization and World Food Program, 2013). Many nations attempting to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) have prioritized ensuring that all children have access to primary education. That was declared by the World Bank in 1999; People live a little better when you give them a hand or a tool, and when you give them an education, they can change the world. As of now, instruction is the basic right of each and every individual because of its commitment, value, variety and enduring harmony (World Training Gathering, 2000).

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) initiative and subsequent conferences by African leaders aimed to address issues such as peace, security, good economic, political, and corporate governance and to make the continent an appealing destination for foreign investment are credited with the introduction of school feeding in Africa. The "New Partnership for African Development" is one of these developments. According to the plan, it is a promise made by African leaders to eliminate poverty, put their countries on the path to sustainable growth and development, and actively participate in the global economy and politics. Additionally, initiatives such as the Millennium Hunger Task Force and the Comprehensive African Agriculture Development Program were intended to link school feeding to agricultural development through the purchase and utilization of locally produced food (Bundy). D, Burbano, C., Grosh, M., Gelli, A. M., Jukes, C.H., and Drake, L.J.2009). One of the nations where hunger has hampered child education significantly is Nigeria. The country has had a very high rate of poverty in the past, and it was recently dubbed the poverty capital of the world (World Poverty Clock, 2019). Most of the poverty is severe in rural areas. Due to their low income, families in these areas typically have trouble sending their children to school. As a result, in order for families to survive, even children need to participate in some kind of activity. As a result, many children of primary and junior secondary school age in food-insecure areas do not attend school. Then again, regardless of whether tutoring is for nothing, families in such regions actually don't possess the ability to take care of certain expenses concerning books, garments, shoes or transportation. These restrictions also prevent children from attending school, encouraging them instead to stay at home and assist their parents with household chores. Therefore, investments in education must target households as well as children in order to address these issues. With the assistance of UNICEF and the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), Nigeria was able to implement the school feeding program in 2005 as one of the 12 pilot countries invited by the Africa Agriculture Development Program (AADP) to do so. As a result, three billion naira was set aside for the program's pilot phase. The program was intended for 3.5 million students attending public primary schools in 12 Nigerian states. Tragically, the program never went past the primary stage. From the 12 states that participated in the program, only Osun and Kano remained shortly after its inception (National Home-Grown School Feeding Program, 2017). While the Participating States are to blame for the non-remittance of counterpart funds, which is a condition for the disbursement of school feeding grants to States, the States blame the UBEC for not releasing funds to the pilot States when due. Regardless of the circumstance, Osun State has maintained the school feeding program up to this point, as Kano State did as well when the federal funding ended in 2008 (Jumare, 2020).

The old school feeding program was the subject of a comprehensive evaluation by the Kebbi State Government in 2015. According to Kebbi State Ministry of Education (2018), the Program was repackaged and officially launched in the State in 2015 with students in Public Primary Schools in Grades 1-3. After seven months, in June, 2016 the Central Government re-dined the program from one side of the country to the other, the program started with 12 states and expanded to 14 states, 22 states, 24 states, and 26 states from the Federation by 2019. The goal is to provide all primary school students in Nigeria with one meal per day with the goals of improving students' health, increasing attendance, encouraging retention, and improving performance. Cited in Jumare, 2020) On January 18, 2016, Governor Atiku Bagudu of Kebbi State flagged off the official start of the free school feeding program at Zannan Gwandu secondary School, Birnin Kebbi local government area of the state. The governor made it clear that the free school feeding program was going to be one of the other benefits of providing education

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and ensuring that every child has access to basic nine years of free education regardless of whether or not his or her parents are financially able. The state's governor also declared free education and free food for junior secondary school students in addition to declaring a state of emergency in the educational sector. This exceptional demonstration added to the expansion in school participation of junior optional school understudies' administration schools (Vanguard News, 2016). However, the Kebbi State Government's School Feeding Program has been the subject of numerous studies. Only a few studies have looked at its effect on attendance, and none of them have combined the impact of SFP and teaching methods on school attendance among junior secondary schools. Subsequently, this study endeavored to fill the gap observed

Education is officially free and compulsory for every child, particularly at the junior secondary stage. The students at this stage were trained to obtain the proficiency that will set them up for a higher degree of schooling. But there is a problem of low attendance especially, in the north-western geopolitical zone of Nigeria in which Kebbi state is inclusive. The north-western states generally and Kebbi state in particular have net attendance rates of 47.7 percent and 29.3 percent, respectively. This indicated that more than half of the children in the region and the state are not in school (UNICEF report, 2021). The education deprivation in Kebbi state is driven by various factors, including economic barriers and socio-cultural norms and practices that discourage attendance in formal education.

Perhaps, Students who attend school regularly have been shown to achieve higher levels in academic attainment than those students who do not have regular attendance. Also, when students attend their classes daily that will install in them the basic value of attending all important event on time. Students, who maintain good attendance, tend to get best in various opportunities that come their way. However, there are several reasons that make some students not attend their classes regularly which could be on health background, economic circumstances, family issues, peer group influence, teachers' poor parental socio-economic status and many more. All of these factors often contribute to the reasons why some students may no longer attend schools regularly and some may eventually drop out totally from schools. Students who missed their classes regularly do not get lucrative career opportunities, and some even turn to a life of crime and even substance abuse as established in many research findings.

To improve school attendance, government introduced school feeding program, the central objective of the program according to Lawal (2011) is to improve school attendance of junior secondary school students in Nigeria and reduce the current dropout rates from junior secondary school, which was estimated to reach 30%. The program also seeks to address the poor nutrition and health status of many children who have been affected as a result of poverty, which has affected the learning outcomes of the children. The Federal Government spent 4.5 billion naira in 2020/21 and 6 billion naira in 2021/22 on school feeding programme. Kebbi State received a total of N499, 985,500 out which all the junior secondary schools across 21 LGAs in the State were fed (Kebbi State Ministry of Education, 2019). Upon this budgetary allocation, the school attendance is still fall below average, especially at the junior secondary school level

In addition, teaching method is also one of the factors that can affect school attendance. Students will be encouraged to attend school because of good teaching methods of their teachers. Considering the fact that teaching method helps students achieve their learning goals, increases student engagement in the classroom, enhances the quality of feedback to students, improves school relationship with families. Considering the relevance and important of teaching methods in improving school attendance there is need for improvement in budgetary allocation to train and re-train teachers in order to improve on their teaching pedagogy, via in-service training, seminar, conferences and workshops. However, many studies have been conducted on school feeding programs and its impact on attendance, retention, and academic performance. But very little or none have been conducted on comparing feeding programs and teaching methods in Kebbi State. This study aims to fill the observed, by comparing feeding programs and teaching methods. It is against this background that the present study investigated the impact of feeding programs and teaching methods on junior secondary school attendance in Kebbi State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of school feeding program and teaching method on junior secondary school students' attendance in Kebbi State. Specifically, the study tends to:

1. Investigate the extent to which SFP influences attendance of junior school students in Kebbi State
2. Examine the extent to which teaching methods influence students' attendance in school.
3. Assess the extent to which school feeding programme affects School attendance in Kebbi State

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of school feeding program on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.
2. There is no significant influence of teaching method on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.
3. The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant influence on Students' attendance.

Methodology

The study used the descriptive research design of expo facto type. However, this design examines the relationship between a dependent variable and an independent variable (groups of participants who already possess certain characteristics prior to the study). The population of this study comprised of all junior secondary school students in Kebbi State. According to Kebbi State Secondary school management board SSMB, (2022), Kebbi State has 323 junior secondary schools with 74,936 students as at the time of this study. Simple random sampling was used to select 10 Junior Secondary Schools. Fifteen (15) students were selected randomly from each of the 10 selected Schools, making total number of samples to be 300.

Three standardized instruments were utilized for the study. These include; School Feeding Program Scale by Akodu, Patrick and Ayodele, (2019).; Teaching Method Scale by Hurriyetoglu, and Kilicoglu, (2020); School Attendance Scale by Yansong Wang and Ichiko Shoji, (2019). The instrument used to measure the participants' perception on school feeding program was a school feeding program instrument developed by Akodu, Patrick and ayodele, (2019). This instrument was adopted and has ten items using a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree with Cronbach alpha of 0.73. Teaching method of participants was measured by adapted teaching method scale which was developed by Hurriyetoglu, and Kilicoglu, (2020). This instrument has fourteen (14) items, with three (3) factors, consisting of visual, auditory and Kinesthetic /tactile categories where visual consist of 6 items, auditory have 5 items and 3 items under kinesthetic. The Cronbach alpha of 0.70 and it has a reliability coefficient scale of 0.87 and the reliability coefficient for the sub factors are 0.816 for visuality, 0.760 for auditory and 0.646 for kinesthetic, using a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree. A test retest was carried out using pilot testing method on 15 students who were not part of the participants and has a Cronbach Alfa of 0.73. The instrument used to measure the participants' view on school attendance was an adapted school attendance scale which was developed by Yansong Wang and Ichiko Shoji, (2019). This instrument comprised twenty-four (24) items, the scale has a total of three (4) factors, consisting of School attraction, Norm, External Pressure and Habit categories. The Cronbach alpha of 0.74 and it has a reliability coefficient scale of 0.832 and the reliability coefficient for the sub factors are 0.80 for school attraction, 0.74 for Norm, 0.75 External pressure and 0.646 for Habit categories, with scoring format of a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree.

The researches with the assistant of other trained research assistance physically went round all the selected schools and administered the questionnaire on the participants; high rate of return was recorded. Data generated for the study were analyzed using frequency statistical method and linear Regression Analysis

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of school feeding program on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

Table 1: Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of School Feeding Program on Student Attendance

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
Constant	33.524	1.851						
School Feeding			.53	10.83	.53	.282	117.25	<.05

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

It was revealed that School Feeding Program has a positive significant influence on Students' attendance rate given the Beta and P value scores to be (B = .531, P = .001). Furthermore, School Feeding Program is responsible for 28.2% variance in Students' attendance (R square = .282). at such we reject the hypothesis which state that "The School Feeding Program has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State".

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of teaching method on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

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Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of visual, kinesthetics, and audio on Student Attendance

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
(Constant)	53.715	1.959						
Visual	.044	.102	.029	.426				
Kinesthetic	.089	.117	.059	.764	.083	.007	0.69	>.05
Audio	-.109	.076	-.112	-1.438				

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

The result revealed that visual, kinesthetics, and audio did not have joint influence on Student Attendance ($R^2 = 0.01$, $F(3,296) = 0.69$, $p > .05$). When combined, visual, kinesthetics, and audio for accounted for 1% of the change observed in the self-report of student Attendance. This revealed that the collective presence of visual, kinesthetics, and audio did not have significant influence on Student Attendance. The result further revealed that visual method of teaching ($\beta = .03$, $t=0.43$ $p > .05$), Kinesthetic ($\beta = .06$, $t=0.76$ $p > .05$) and Audio method of teaching ($\beta = -.11$, $t=-1.44$ $p > .05$) were not significant independent predictors of student attendance. The hypothesis is thus accepted.

Hypothesis 3

The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant influence on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

Table3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of visual, kinesthetic, audio and School feeding program on Student Attendance.

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
(Constant)	35.932	2.331						
Visual	-.027	.087	-.018	-.306				
Kinesthetic	-.016	.100	-.011	-.159	.54	.29	30.18	<.05
Audio	-.072	.065	-.073	-1.109				
School feeding program	.635	.058	.538	10.856				

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

The result revealed that visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program have joint influence on Student Attendance ($R^2 = 30.18$, $F(4,295) = 0.69$, $p < .05$). When combined visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program for accounted for 29% of the change observed in the self-report of student Attendance. This revealed that the collective presence of visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program have significant influence on Student Attendance. The result further revealed that only school feeding program ($\beta = .54$, $t=10.86$ $p < .05$) have significant independent predictor on school attendance while visual ($\beta = -.02$, $t=-0.31$ $p > .05$), kinesthetic ($\beta = -.01$, $t=-0.16$ $p > .05$) and Audio method of teaching ($\beta = -.07$ $t=-1.109$; $p > .05$) were not significant independent predictors of student attendance. As such we refute the hypothesis which states that "The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State".

Discussion of findings

This study aims to investigate the impact of the school feeding program and teaching method on junior secondary school attendance in Kebbi State. The first hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between school feeding program and Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State, was confirmed by the results, which showed that the school feeding program has a significant positive impact on the attendance rate of students in Kebbi State, the hypothesis is therefore rejected and alternative hypothesis was accepted that there is significant difference between school feeding program and attendance. The result of this finding is in line findings of Elijah Yendaw and Frederick (2015), which established positive impact of school feeding on attendance among school going children in Ghana. They emphasized that one of the social interference programs established to raise educational values in rural Ghanaian communities is the Ghana School Feeding Programme (GSFP). The principal objective of the program is to sharpen guardians on advantage of school participation, further develop participation, make junior optional school understudies stay in schools and to work on the healthful admission of kids in both rustic and metropolitan regions. Since 2005, the Nyoglo community in the Savelugu-Nanton Municipality, which had the lowest rates of student attendance and retention, has benefited from this social intervention.

The second hypothesis stated that there is no significant difference between teaching method and Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State. The result however confirmed that there is significant difference between teaching method and school

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attendance, therefore, the hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The findings of this study is against the resolutions of Enamiroro's (2010) research, which sought to determine the average percentage of students who attended school, their academic performance, and the relationship between attendance and academic performance in secondary schools, the findings showed that the teaching method did not have a significant impact on students' attendance. An agenda was utilized to gather 2860 understudies' rate scores in participation and scholastic execution from 58 optional schools, utilized in this review. Using a percentage mean and a linear regression equation, three research questions were answered. Two speculations were formed and tried utilizing Pearson r. That's what the review uncovered; the mean score for attendance was 68%, and the mean score for academic performance was 66%. Additionally, it demonstrated a moderately positive relationship between academic performance and attendance. The coefficient of determination, $r^2 = 0.22$, indicated that attendance at secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria, influenced the academic performance of 22% of students, (Enamiroro, 2010).

The third hypothesis stated that the School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State. The results therefore confirmed and established a positive relationship between school feeding program, teaching method and school attendance. This is in line with conclusion of Shabani (2018), who assessed the impact of the SFP on the academic performance of students in Mlunduzi ward, Tanzania, it was discovered that the combination of the teaching method and the school feeding program has a significant impact on the school enrolment. The cross-sectional review configuration was utilized for this review. The nature of this study was both qualitative and quantitative. In order to gather data on the impact, a survey was sent to 96 students from four primary schools in the Mlunduzi ward that were chosen at random.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrated that the school feeding program has a significant and positive impact on student attendance. As stated by other studies, despite some studies indicating an increase in the number of meals served, numerous studies have demonstrated the program's positive impact on attendance. Additionally, it has been observed that teaching method has a significant impact on student attendance because students have a greater tendency to look forward to not missing class in the future when they learn and feel at ease with the format or lecture.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The study, recommends that government and other stakeholders in-charge of SFP should remain committed towards the provision of necessary resources for the smooth running of the programme so as to improve the educational infrastructure of rural communities.
2. Government should consider the sustainability of the school feeding program that provides nutritious meals to students. This program can help to improve attendance by addressing the issue of hunger and malnutrition among students. When students have access to healthy and nutritious food, they are more likely to attend school regularly and perform better academically.
3. Effective teaching methods are essential for keeping students engaged and interested in learning. Teachers should use interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, problem-solving exercises, and hands-on activities to make learning more interesting and engaging. This will help to keep students motivated to attend school and participate in classroom activities.
4. Parents and community members can play a vital role in promoting regular attendance among junior secondary school students. Schools should involve parents and community members in school activities and encourage them to take an active role in supporting their children's education. This can include attending parent-teacher conferences, volunteering at school events, and advocating for education in the community.

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